

Recent TipESM Activities

TipESM Annual Meeting and joint meeting with OptimESM

TipESM and OptimESM joined forces in the beginning of June at the Danish Meteorological Institute in Copenhagen for two days of tipping point science. The joint meeting included exciting presentations, sharing of new findings and results from both projects, and hands-on workshops on Earth System Models, capitalizing on the synergies between the two projects.

TipESM hosted its annual meeting on 4 June, the day after the joint meeting. The day was full of updates across tasks, as well as hands-on collaboration on activities, discussions and aligning on next steps.

TipESM Outreach Event in Copenhagen

When in Copenhagen, TipESM hosted an outreach event on tipping points at the Royal Danish Library for local stakeholders in Denmark. Here TipESM and OptimESM researchers: Shuting Yang, Torben Koenigk, Didier Swingedouw and Andrew Hartley shared key findings on tipping point mechanisms and connections, the risks they pose, and their potential impacts on society and ecosystems.

[Read the 10 key takeaways from the outreach event on zenodo here](#)

Recent TipESM Activities

TipESM policy briefing: The potential tipping of the Amazon rainforest

On 23 April 2026 TipESM delivered a policy briefing to the Brazilian government on the potential tipping of the Amazon rainforest.

TipESM is producing a range of new climate simulations specifically designed to assess the sensitivity of the Amazon rainforest to global warming. Climate model simulations suggest that the rainforest could collapse into a savanna-like state across a wide range of temperatures, from 2°C to 6°C of global warming above pre-industrial levels, with the most likely range between 3°C and 4°C.

Read the factsheet here:

['The Amazon: A Potential Tipping Point in The Earth's Climate System'](#)

Register of the Early Warning Indicators

In a newly published TipESM deliverable, we bring together knowledge from across the scientific literature, including methods developed within TipESM, to present a comprehensive register of early warning indicators (EWIs) for key climate tipping elements, including the AMOC, the SPG, the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets and Arctic sea ice.

This work contributes to the broader effort to better understand, monitor, and anticipate climate tipping risks.

[Read the deliverable here](#)

Toolbox for identifying emerging constraints

As part of TipESM, researchers have developed ClimLoco 1.0, which is a new statistical toolbox designed to identify and apply observational constraints for different tipping elements. The framework improves how uncertainties are quantified, accounts for observational errors and internal variability, and enables the use of multiple predictors to better understand future changes in key climate variables. This supports TipESM's work to improve projections and uncertainty estimates for major climate tipping elements.

[Read the milestone report here](#)

JPI Meeting in Brussels: 2nd Writing workshop of “AMOC in Focus” initiative

A second writing workshop for the joint initiative ‘AMOC in Focus’ by JPI Climate and JPI Oceans to undertake a Scientific Assessment will be held in Brussels at the Royal Meteorological Institute situated in Uccle, from 29 June to 2 July 2026. Several TipESM researchers are involved in the report.

The initiative will result in a scientific assessment report examining the current state and evolution of the AMOC, future projections, evidence for possible tipping points, potential impacts on climate, ecosystems, and societies, as well as adaptation, mitigation, and governance solutions.

July ClimTip webinar:

Climate, carbon cycle and biogeochemical responses to a 21st century AMOC Collapse under a 2°C Stabilization Pathway

In the July ClimTip webinar, TipESM’s Thomas Frölicher, who is one of the Lead Authors of the WGI chapter on tipping points of the IPCC AR7 cycle, will talk about the effects of an AMOC collapse this century under a 2°C stabilization scenario. The webinar is open to everyone.

Speaker: Thomas Frölicher

Date: 7 July, 2026

Time: 2:00–3:00 pm CEST

[Webinar Link \(Teams\) - join here](#)

TipESM wishes you a great summer!

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